

12th International Meeting on Antimicrobial Peptides

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– 27/08/2025

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Event Sponsors

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Summary

The 12th International Meeting on Antimicrobial Peptides (IMAP 2025) took place in the Royal College of Surgeons (RCSI), located in the heart of the vibrant city center of Dublin from the 25th to the 27th of August 2025. (peptideconferences.org/imap2025/home). This annual Meeting, which began in 2008 in Leipzig, has seen a growing number of participants over the years, particularly young scientists interested in peptide science. The 2025 event in Dublin, attracted about 100 attendees from all over the world. The 2025 meeting covered a range of topics within the field of antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), including design & synthesis, data mining, mechanism of action and resistance, immunomodulation and therapeutic applications.

As with previous IMAPs, it was agreed that such a meeting should promote the participation of PhD students and postdocs offering them plenty of space to present their skills and to divulge the results of their scientific work. This has stimulated intensive

interaction among them and prompted the establishment of scientific collaborations as well as interpersonal relationships. Attendance of early-stage researchers was helped by the organisers being able to offer 13 travel bursaries, funded by the generous support of our sponsors, to PhD students and postdocs who were presenting posters or talks.

Attendees

The meeting attracted 96 participants from 20 countries from Europe, USA, Canada, Australia, Chile, and India. We hosted 39 academics, 12 post-Docs, 35 PhD students, and 10 industrialists.

Target audience: Academics, early-career researchers, postgraduate students, industrialists

Programme

The scientific programme consisted of 6 sessions focusing on Mode of Action, Prediction and Design of AMPs; AMP structure and membrane interactions; AI / non-AI supported database mining; AMP Resistance; Applications of AMPs in Therapeutics and Biomaterials; Lantibiotics and Non-ribosomal Antimicrobial Peptides and 2 extensive poster sessions. 7 invited lectures were given by the following speakers in the beautiful Albert Lecture Theatre. Prof Annelise Barron, Stanford University, who spoke about: “Antimicrobial peptoids: Emerging internationally as versatile, broad-spectrum, biostable, safe mimics of host defense peptides.” Prof César de la Fuente, University of Pennsylvania, who spoke about “Accelerating antibiotic discovery using AI”. Prof. Colin Hill, University College Cork, who spoke about “Manipulating the microbiome with lantibiotics”. Prof. Fintan Kelleher, Technological University of Dublin, who spoke about “The lantibiotic nisin – can the tail wag the dog?” Prof. Jean-Louis Reymond, University of Bern, who spoke about the “Chemical Space for Antimicrobial Peptide Design”. Prof. Anne van der Does, Leiden University Medical Center, who spoke about “Advanced Lung Cell Culture Models to Study the effects of AMPs on Infections, Host Defense and Tissue Repair”. Prof. Gerard Wong, UCLA, who spoke about ‘Beyond antimicrobial activity: How AMP like peptide motifs can mechanistically mediate inflammatory, cardiovascular, and rheumatic pathologies’.

Further, the Scientific Board selected 16 speakers for oral presentations and 14 speakers for rapid oral presentations from the pool of the submitted abstracts and 31 poster presentations altogether.

At the end of day 1 there was also a Careers Workshop where Prof. Anne van der Does, Dr. Marina Rubini, Dr. Johanna Mbianda and Ms Freyja O’Duffy shared with PhD and postdocs their experience on different career pathways and engaged in an open discussion with the participants.

The poster sessions took place on the 1st and 2nd day of the meeting in an enjoyable and relaxed atmosphere.

The social events of IMAP included 5 coffee-breaks, 1 welcome reception, 1 social dinner and 3 lunches, all held in the beautiful premises of RCSI.

Prizes

Two juries selected the two best posters and the two best rapid communications for early carrier

researchers. The prizes were presented at the end of the conference by Dr. Marina Rubini, representing the Protein & Peptide Science Group of the Royal Society of Chemistry (sponsor of the poster and short oral competitions).

Poster Prizes (Figure 1):

- 1st place Renke Itzenga, University of Leipzig for his poster “Analysis of Peptides based on the Proline-rich Antimicrobial Peptides Api137 and Onc112”.
- 2nd place Libbi Moon, Durham University for her poster “Structure-Activity Relationship Insights of Antimicrobial Peptoid Library”.

Figure 1. Winner (left) and runner-up (right) of Poster competition.

Best Short Oral Communications (Figure 2)

- 1st place Negar Yazdani, University of Melbourne, for her paper “Protease Activity and Anaerobic Environment Alter Antimicrobial Efficacy of SNAPPs: Implications for Targeting Biofilms and Peri-Implantitis”.
- 2nd place Sergi Llanet Ferrer, Universitat de Girona for her paper “Membrane interaction mechanisms of BP100, 1036, and FV7 explored via molecular dynamics”.

Figure 2. Winner (left) and runner-up (right) of Oral Communication competition.

We would like to conclude with a picture of the happy participants of IMAP 2025 (Figure 3) and we are looking forward to another successful event!

Figure 3. Group photo of Participants of the 12th IMAP.

Previous Events in this Series

Reports of several of the previous IMAP meetings are available from the European Peptide Society website, as well as other sources:

12th IMAP (Marina Rubini, Marc Devocelle), 12 October 2025, Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland www.eurpepsoc.com/a-report-on-the-12th-international-meeting-on-antimicrobial-peptides-imap-2025/

11th IMAP (Alethea Tabor, James Mason, Kai Hilpert), 26 September 2024, Kings College London, www.eurpepsoc.com/a-report-on-the-11th-international-meeting-on-antimicrobial-peptides-imap-2024/

10th IMAP (Marialuisa Mangoni), 9 October 2023, University of Trieste, www.eurpepsoc.com/a-report-on-the-10th-international-meeting-on-antimicrobial-peptides-imap/

9th IMAP (Maria Luisa Mangoni), 18 September 2019, University of Utrecht, www.eurpepsoc.com/report-9th-international-meeting-antimicrobial-peptides/

Journal of Peptide Science: Volume 24, Issue 7: Special Issue dedicated to the 7th International Meeting on Antimicrobial Peptides held in Copenhagen on 25-27 August 2017-Chairmen: Paul Robert Hansen and Håvard Jenssen